

EDEN ISS

Software Interface Document

prepared for

WP 2.1 - System Requirements & Interface Analysis

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Executive summary

This document provides the system software interface requirements of the EDEN ISS project.

It includes the definition of all EDEN ISS external and internal software interface requirements. This includes a definition of telemetry from EDEN ISS sensors and telecommands used for controlling specific EDEN ISS equipment, EDEN ISS synoptic displays.

Table of contents

Executive summary	3
Table of contents	4
Acronyms	5
1 Introduction.....	6
1.1 Overall objectives of the EDEN ISS project.....	6
1.2 Summary state-of-the-art: Bio-regenerative life support systems and architecture	6
2 Terms, definitions, conventions.....	8
2.1 Definitions and terms	8
2.2 Conventions	16
2.2.1 Units	16
3 Antarctic environment as analogue test site	17
3.1 Description of Antarctic environment	17
3.2 Neumayer Station III as a space analogue site for testing EDEN ISS mobile test facility	17
3.3 Polarstern and Neumayer Station III Transport and Crane Limits.....	18
4 EDEN ISS Software interface requirements	19
4.1 Software applications	19
4.1.1 EDEN ISS control software.....	19
4.1.2 ISPR control software	19
4.1.3 EDEN ISS controlled sensors and actuators.....	20
4.1.4 EDEN ISS Displays	20
4.2 EDEN ISS external communications	21
4.2.1 EDEN ISS Control Network and Ground Systems	21
5 References.....	49
5.1 Applicable Documents.....	49
5.2 Reference Documents	49

Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
AD	Applicable Document	ISS	International Space Station
AIT	Assembly, Integration and Test	LabVIEW	Laboratory Virtual Instrument Engineering Workbench
AMS	Air Management System	LED	Light Emitting Diode
AWI	Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research	MTF	Mobile Test Facility
BLSS	Bio-regenerative Life Support Systems	NDS	Nutrient Delivery System
CDH	Command and Data Handling	NM-III	Neumayer Station III
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	PDS	Power Distribution System
DAQ	Data Acquisition	RD	Reference Document
EC	Electrical Conductivity	REC	Recirculation
ECC	EDEN ISS Control Centre	RUCOLA	Rack-like Unit for Consistent on-Orbit Leafy crops Availability
EDR	European Drawer Rack	SRD	Systems Requirement Document
E-Nose	Electronic Nose	SS	Service Section
EP	Elevated Platform	TAS-I	Thales Alenia Space Italia S.p.A.
ESA	European Space Agency	TBC	To Be Clarified
ESC	External Storage Container	TBD	To Be Determined
EU	European Union	TCS	Thermal Control System
FEG	Future Exploration Greenhouse	TPZ	Telespazio S.p.A.
FREE	Freecooler	TRL	Technology Readiness Level
FW	Fresh Water	UHB	User Home Base
HP	High Pressure	UIP	Utility Interface Panel
ISPR	International Standard Payload Rack	WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Overall objectives of the EDEN ISS project

Long-term human presence in space will require the development of bio-regenerative life support systems (BLSS). The integration of such systems into manned habitats decreases the resupply requirements by generating human resources via biological processes. The EDEN ISS project aims to validate selected subsystems and key technologies up to a TRL of 6 according to the standards described in the Technology Readiness Levels Handbook for Space Applications of the European Space Agency (ESA) [RD1]. Therefore the project will demonstrate operational capability of key technologies in an environment with some characteristics relevant to space. For this purpose a dedicated test campaign will be executed at the Neumayer Station III in Antarctica where a deployed mobile test facility will be operated by an isolated overwintering crew. This deployment will also be preparatory research for a future plant production system at the ISS.

The main objectives of EDEN ISS are shown in Table 1-1.

Table 1-1: Objectives of the EDEN ISS project

Objective 1	Manufacturing a space analogue mobile test facility to provide representative mass flows and proper test environments for plant cultivation technologies as an essential on-ground preparatory activity for future space exploration.
Objective 2	Integration and test of key elements for plant cultivation in 1) an ISPR-like system (International Standard Payload Rack) for future test on-board ISS and 2) a Future Exploration Greenhouse (FEG) to prepare for closed-loop bio-regenerative life support systems.
Objective 3	Adaption, integration, fine-tuning and demonstration of key technologies and their functionality in respective laboratory environments and (under highly isolated conditions) in an Antarctic environment.
Objective 4	Development and demonstration of operation techniques and processes for higher plant cultivation to achieve reliable and safe production of high-quality food.
Objective 5	Study of microbial behavior and countermeasures in plant-based closed ecosystems and their impacts on isolated crews.
Objective 6	Actively advancing knowledge related to human spaceflight and transformation of research results into terrestrial applications , by actively leveraging synergies between space and non-space consortium partners.

1.2 Summary state-of-the-art: Bio-regenerative life support systems and architecture

The unique aspect of EDEN ISS is the focus on the key technologies and procedures associated with higher plant cultivation and high quality safe food production. This means that instead of dealing with all the different aspects of a BLSS, the envisioned project focuses on an essential target area. Targeting only this area guarantees a higher scientific outcome than spreading the research focus too broadly. Therefore, the EDEN ISS consortium will advance the current state-of-the-art through several means:

- Develop a **high fidelity ISPR cultivation system with approximately 1 m² production area**, thereby enhancing the feasibility of Europe providing the ISS with a plant production facility capable of almost an order of magnitude increase to current orbit production areas.
- Deploy a European constructed, **highly integrated, mobile greenhouse module test facility to Antarctica**. After completion of the project, the test facility will be used for further on-going BLSS investigations and will be open for experiments to the European BLSS community.
- Increase the TRL of a **microgravity NDS** built with materials capable of reducing possible biological contamination and including **advanced on-line ion-selective sensors**.
- Advance the TRL of **spectrally tunable LED lighting systems** for highly reliable and remotely operated plant production systems. Energy conservation will be improved through the development and use of **advanced LED heat capture techniques and intra-canopy lighting**. Experimentally determine

optimal light recipes for 5-10 crops and employ these recipes to maximize production within the mobile test facility.

- Increase of the TRL of relevant technologies in the field of **bio-detection and decontamination** of BLSS.
- Further develop proper **plant handling and food safety procedures** for higher plant cultivation in closed systems comparable to ISS and future long-duration space missions.

Table 1-2 provides a summary of the specific advances to the current state-of-the-art for the primary focus areas of the EDEN ISS project.

Table 1-2: Overview and comparison between state-of-the-art and beyond state-of-the-art

System	State-of-the-art	Beyond state-of-the-art
Greenhouse module test facility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simple ‘Salad Machines’, small food quantities • Cultivation processes and plant health monitoring is rather hands-on with limited automation • Bulk of Antarctic systems have been expeditioner/hobby- based and constructed with materials found on-site • Limited to no remote commanding • Single surface production systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produce higher quantities of fresh crops in order to achieve higher mission fidelity • Highly integrated test module, considering all necessary subsystems and analyzing the overall mass production principles • Detailed quantification of pre- and post-processing analysis, cleaning and general crew time allocations • Enhance reliability of remote greenhouses through telepresence (tools and competency)
ISS plant production facility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small-scale production areas (~0.1 m²) • Science driven • Negligible food production • Low to marginal environmental control reliability (some exceptions) • Non-scalable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medium-scale production areas (~1 m²) • Food production and psychological benefit driven • Non-negligible food production for repeatable safety evaluation • Well characterized and reliable environmental control • Scalable
Nutrient delivery system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil-based and soilless cultivation • On-line nutrient solution status measurements are indiscriminate (e.g. electrical conductivity) • Off-line measurements of ion-selective values are time intensive (e.g. days/ weeks) • Difficult and insufficient bio-contamination prevention 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soilless cultivation is imperative • Higher yield, low water and nutrient use systems • Real-time online measurements of selective ion concentrations (e.g. new optrodes) • View of root system enhances ability of remote telemetric monitoring (e.g. aeroponic) • Nanostructured coatings for bio-contamination prevention onto surfaces
Light system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct natural light (Sun) not feasible for space greenhouses (e.g. radiation, temporal variability, system complexity) • Fluorescent, high pressure sodium, metal halide, Sulphur plasma lamp, induction lamp • PAR-specific multispectral LED light most promising candidate, but in early development stage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High performance LEDs (combining a variety of monochromatic lights, specifically tailored to plant photosynthetic requirements) • Highly integrated panels and optimized with respect to mass, thermal load (active cooled), volume, and power demand • Intra-canopy lighting systems
Bio-detection and decontamination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bio-detection performed by classical sampling method, wiping followed by incubation in a sample medium • Work intensive spray and wipe decontamination procedures, physico-chemical treatment or steam disinfection of small items • No possibility to disinfect hard-to-reach areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time detection of quality and quantity of microbial loads (using gas-analyzing instrument E-Nose) • High reachability (e.g. cavities, tubes and harnesses) with TransMADDS • Specific decontaminant depending on the microbial load, preventive effect, no damage of equipment
Food quality and safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensory evaluation of food products for characterization of texture, flavor and palatability • Nutrient determination via solvent extraction and analysis via laboratory scale atomic absorption spectroscopy, liquid chromatography and UV-Visible spectroscopy • Lab based PCR or standard plate count techniques and microscopy employed for identification of microbial and infectious agents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish sensor panel response versus physio-metric data analysis to produce a sensory evaluation protocol for use on board ISS • Rapid, non-destructive indicators of food quality • Rapid screen for microbial contamination • Food safety quick tests; new palatability analysis tools • Increase shelf lifetime for produced crops

2 Terms, definitions, conventions

2.1 Definitions and terms

Figure 2-1: Overview of EDEN ISS Mobile Test Facility (MTF) main elements.

EDEN ISS Elements

Mobile Test Facility (MTF)

The EDEN ISS mobile test facility to be operated in the Antarctic at the Neumayer Station III for testing a food production system under mission relevant conditions at ISS and future planetary outposts. The MTF comprises 2 x 20 ft high-cube shipping containers joined together at their front ends. The MTF is oriented in East-West direction. (see Figure 2-1).

Service Section Container

The Service Section Container houses the main entrance at its West front end, which leads into the cold porch (or air lock) and from there on into the Service Section. The East front end of the Service Section Container is connected to the West front end of the FEG Container (see Figure 2-1). The Service Section Container also contains a raised floor on which the normal working area is located. The space below the raised floor is called the sub-floor.

Cold Porch (= air lock)

An enclosed section in the Service Section Container of the MTF that provides a climatic interface buffer between the external environment and the MTF service sec-

tion (see Figure 2-1). Used for changing clothing (weather gear to lab clothing), general storage and housing the waste liquid and fresh water tank in the sub-floor.

Service Section (SS)

The Service Section is housed in the Service Section Container (see Figure 2-1). The Service Section houses the ISPR cultivation system. Furthermore, the Service Section contains all utilities for the MTF such as power distribution, Air Management System, Thermal Control System, Nutrient Delivery System, and consoles/computers for controlling MTF, FEG and ISPR. The SS also provides a work environment for visiting personnel including desk/chair/locker and sink.

International Standard Payload Rack (ISPR) Cultivation System

The EDEN ISS ISPR is a ground version of the standard payload racks used on ISS. It provides all resources such as power, environmental and thermal control, nutrient delivery and data management to support 2 plant cultivation chambers for simultaneous cultivation of different plants under different environmental conditions.

FEG Container

The FEG Container houses the Future Exploration Greenhouse. The West front end of the FEG Container is connected to the East front end of the Service Section Container. The East front end of the FEG Container houses an emergency exit. The FEG Container also contains a raised floor on which the normal working area is located. The space below the raised floor is called the sub-floor.

Future Exploration Greenhouse (FEG)

The FEG is installed within the FEG Container. It contains rack structures mounted along the sides of the container (4 each side). Each rack can be configured with up to 4 shelves for accommodating Plant Grow Units, LED lighting, LED water cooling, nutrient delivery hardware, sensors and cameras. Also contains space in a rack for seed germination. The FEG is separated from the SS by a sealed wall. A door is provided for access from the SS. An Emergency Exit door is available at the far end of the FEG.

MTF Internal – General

Raised Floor

Both containers of the MTF have a raised floor which is around 30 cm above the original container floor. The raised floor is held by a stainless steel structure and is the normal walking and working surface, therefore the stainless steel framework is covered with floor panels. The space below the raised floor is called the sub-floor.

Sub-Floor

Space between container floor and raised floor. The free height of the subfloor is around 25 cm throughout the whole MTF. The sub-floor contains the fresh and waste water tanks inside the Cold Porch and air tubes and liquid pipes within the Service Section and the FEG. The sub-

	<i>floor also contains a drainage basin in the Service Section and the FEG.</i>
Floor Panels	<i>The floor panels cover the raised floor and functions as the normal walking and working surface.</i>
Drainage Basin (= "sump")	<i>The drainage basin is located in the sub-floor of the service section and the FEG. Its purpose is to collect spilled or leaked fluids. Collected liquids are drained via pump to waste liquid tank housed in cold porch sub-floor.</i>
Wall and Ceiling Cladding	<i>Interior wall panelling that protects the MTF insulation from humidity and spilled liquids.</i>
Container-to-Container Interface	<i>Insulated space between containers for mating joints, utility piping, electric/sensor harness connectors etc.</i>

MTF Internal – Cold Porch

Main Entrance Door	<i>Main door for access to MTF. Weather sealed door with small window.</i>
Cold Porch Heaters	<i>Heater(s) in the cold porch that automatically are ON when airlock ambient temperature falls below 5°C.</i>
Cold Porch locker	<i>Container for clothing, personnel items etc. (external weather gear, lab clothing etc.).</i>
Waste Liquid Tank	<i>300 l (approx.) tank housed in sub-floor of the Cold Porch for temporary storage of all liquid waste from the MTF.</i>
Fresh Water Tank	<i>300 l (approx.) tank housed in sub-floor of the Cold Porch for storage of fresh water for the MTF.</i>

MTF Internal – Service Section

Service Section Entrance Door	<i>Door connecting the cold porch with the Service Section.</i>
Service Section General Lighting	<i>Overhead white light source fulfilling standard for office illumination at desk level.</i>
Service Section Window	<i>Rectangular window on the North side of the Service Section above desk facing the NM-III.</i>
Atmosphere Management System (AMS)	<i>The AMS is an automated system that actively controls a pre-determined air flow speed, temperature and composition to the FEG via air ducts and dedicated louvers. FEG atmospheric parameters monitored by the AMS are CO₂, temperature and relative humidity. Exhaust air is cycled back to the AMS from the FEG via air ducts. The AMS then controls the humidity, and temperature of the returned airflow and sterilizes using UV and filters with a combination of a pre-filter, HEPA and charcoal filter (e.g., for ethylene) prior to cycling back to the FEG (which, to the extent possible, has a closed atmospheric environment). The AMS also has a separate Service Section air control system, which uses external air drawn into the Service Section as a source of fresh air (controlled for temperature and humidity)..</i>

Argus	<p><i>The Argus System is an all-in-one hardware and software platform for instrumentation monitoring, data acquisition, data logging, alarms, and automated equipment control. EDEN ISS uses Argus for monitoring and control of the Nutrient Delivery System, Atmosphere Management System, Thermal Control System and overall MTF system.</i></p>
Nutrient Delivery System (NDS)	<p><i>An automatic system for supplying nutrient feed to the Plant Cultivation Units in the FEG. The NDS comprises 2 individual bulk nutrient solutions that can be automatically modified with respect to acid, base and nutrient salt concentration prior to being pumped to the FEG Plant Cultivation Units. The NDS monitors and controls the nutrient composition for electrical conductivity (EC), dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, ion-selective concentrations (specific ions TBD), temperature and ozone concentration (measurement in air - for safety purposes). The bulk nutrient solutions are stored in two 250 L tanks. Fresh water is supplied to the nutrient mixing system from an approximate 300 L tank. Waste liquids are pumped to the waste tank in the subfloor of the Cold Porch. The NDS is monitored and controlled via the Argus computer.</i></p>
Nutrient Tank(s)	<p><i>Two 250 L tanks each containing a specific bulk nutrient solution for the Nutrient Delivery System (NDS).</i></p>
Power Distribution System	<p><i>The Power Distribution System (PDS) distributes a stabilized 230 VAC power supply to all of the MTF elements requiring electrical power. The PDS also provides 24 VDC and 12 VDC power to selective systems such as the ISPR. The PDS is connected to the Neumayer Station III overall electrical power supply of 230 VAC by land cable.</i></p>
Thermal Control System (TCS)	<p><i>The Thermal Control System (TCS) provides individual water-cooling for the Atmosphere Management System (AMS), the ISPR and the LED panels in the FEG Plant Grow Units. The TCS provides water to each of these cooling loops at a pre-defined temperature. The return flow temperature is monitored by the TCS and the system automatically adjusts a set of three-way valves to ensure sufficient cooling. Waste heat is removed via heat exchangers in each TCS loop and cycled outside of the MTF via separate fluid loops (water + Tyfocor) to a passive external radiator mounted on the top of the MTF. The TCS is monitored and controlled via the Argus computer.</i></p>
Uninterruptible Power Supply	<p><i>The Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) provides emergency power to specific systems in case of main power failure from the Neumayer Station III. Presently designed to provide 1400W for 36 – 115 minutes (depending on number of modules) at 70% load.</i></p>

MTF Internal – ISPR

ISPR Cold Plate	<i>A water cooled plate for mounting items that need removal of excess heat during operation.</i>
ISPR Drawer	<i>A dedicated removable drawer in the ISPR for housing payloads. Each drawer is provided with standard interface resources such as power, thermal cooling, data handling etc. The number of available drawers is dependent upon the design function of the ISPR</i>
ISPR Fire Alarm LED	<i>Red LED smoke/fire light on front of ISPR that is activated by interior smoke sensor in case of fire.</i>
LabVIEW	<i>LabVIEW (Laboratory Virtual Instrument Engineering Workbench) is a system-design platform and development environment for a visual programming language from National Instruments. The EDEN ISS ISPR uses this application for monitoring and control of all the ISPR sensor parameters.</i>
Plant Cultivation Chamber	<i>A dedicated plant grow unit housed in a drawer of the ISPR. There are 2x chambers in the ISPR, one for short plants and one for tall plants. Each chamber contains a root zone, a plant growth zone and a LED illumination panel. Each chamber has provision for nutrient feed to the root zone, CO₂ and fresh air to the plant zone as well as water cooling and electrical power for the LEDs. The chambers are monitored by sensors via the ISPR LabVIEW computer application software for CO₂ and relative humidity in the plant growth zone as well as soil temperature, moisture, and electrical conductivity in the root zone. Two video cameras are provided in each chamber to monitor overall plant health.</i>
Rack Maintenance Switch	<i>A 2-position manually operated switch that when set in open position cuts all power to ISPR. Used to assure safety of personnel when accessing inside of ISPR for maintenance purposes etc.</i>
Utility Interface Panel (UIP)	<i>Interface panel at base of ISPR for connecting external utilities such as water, power, data etc. via ISPR standard connectors.</i>

Future Exploration Greenhouse (FEG)

FEG Entrance Door	<i>Door connecting service section with the Future Exploration Greenhouse (FEG).</i>
Emergency Exit	<i>Weather sealed door that connects FEG to exterior platform. During normal operations only to be used during fire or chemical emergency if path to main door in airlock is not accessible (may be used for basic facility access during the construction and test phases).</i>
FEG General Lighting	<i>Overhead dimmable white light source fulfilling standard for office illumination at desk level.</i>

Aeroponics	<i>Aeroponics is the process of growing plants in an air or mist environment without the use of soil or an aggregate medium.</i>
Hydroponics	<i>Hydroponics is a subset of hydroculture and is a method of growing plants using mineral nutrient solutions, in water, without soil. Terrestrial plants may be grown with their roots in the mineral nutrient solution only, or in an inert medium, such as perlite or gravel.</i>
LED Panel	<i>A single LED lamp with variable light output from 150 - 600 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ and individual wavelength setting all controlled by Ethernet commanding/monitoring via Argus computer in Service Section. The lamps are water cooled via the MTF Thermal Control System. One LED panel is utilized per single Plant Growth Unit (except in the instance of intracanopy lighting).</i>
Photosynthetically Active Radiation	<i>The Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) designates the spectral range (wave band) of solar radiation from 400 to 700 nanometers that photosynthetic organisms are able to use in the process of photosynthesis.</i>
Louver	<i>An opening in the incoming FEG air ducts that can be manually controlled to manipulate the airflow in the plants. Each horizontal FEG air duct includes 8 louvers.</i>

Figure 2-2: Overview of Plant Grow Unit components and topology of FEG Plant Grow Racks.

Plant Grow Chamber	<i>An alternative terminology for the interior of the FEG.</i>
Plant Grow Rack	<i>A standard rack structure in the FEG comprising shelves for accommodating the Plant Grow Units. There are in total eight Plant Grow Racks in the FEG, four on the left (North) side and four on the right (South) side. Each rack is individually numbered as follows: When facing Emergency Exit from FEG door, the racks on the left (North) side are numbered L1, L2, L3 and L4, those on the right (South) side R1, R2, R3 and R4. Each rack can be individually configured with up to 8 Plant Grow Units (see Figure 2-2).</i>
Plant Growth Level	<i>The level in the Plant Grow Unit that separates the plant root volume in the Plant Grow Trays from the plant foliage section (see Figure 2-2).</i>
Plant Grow Unit	<i>A standard plant growth dedicated volume available in various heights (52 cm, 104 cm and 208 cm) dependent on plant size. The unit comprises from top to bottom; an LED panel with water cooling, a plant leaf section, a Plant Grow Tray with holes for shoots and a root zone with an aeroponics nutrient delivery system. Each Unit is numbered either 1, 2, 3 or 4 from bottom to top depending on configuration. For example the first rack on the left side has 4 Plant Grow Units and is therefore numbered L1-1, L1-2, L1-3 and L1-4 from bottom to top.</i>
Plant Grow Tray	<i>A standard plant growing tray, 40 cm by 60 cm, comprises an enclosed lower Root Zone section for housing the plant root system and nutrient delivery diffusers. The upper surface of the Root Zone section has various hole sizes/number depending on plant height/ species and is termed the Shoot Zone (see Figure 2-2).</i>
Seed Germination Unit	<i>A dedicated unit for germinating seeds prior to transfer of shoots to Plant Grow Units. Will be housed in the left-hand side end rack, position L4 (see Figure 2-2).</i>
<u>MTF External</u>	
Platform External Walkway	<i>Walkway on platform around the perimeter of the MTF.</i>
Safety Railing	<i>Railing for safety purposes on sides of MTF access stairs, platform walkway perimeter, and a portion of the MTF roof.</i>
MTF Access Stairs	<i>Stairway with safety rails allowing personnel access from ground to elevated platform level and the MTF entrance hatch.</i>
Door Lighting	<i>Lighting mounted over the top of the main entrance and the emergency exit doors to illuminate the space in front of the respective door.</i>

Platform External Lighting	<i>Fixed lighting around perimeter of MTF.</i>
MTF Roof Access Ladder	<i>Vertical ladder for access to roof of MTF mounted (but likely to be transportable) on the West side of the West-container to the right of the main entrance.</i>
Free Cooler	<i>Roof-mounted system using fans to reject excess heat from internal MTF thermal control system into the external environment. Heat load from MTF transported to free cooler via fluid line. Fluid qualified down to -50 degC.</i>
WLAN Antenna	<i>Wireless LAN antenna for data communications between MTF and NM-III housed externally on MTF container roof.</i>
External Utility Connector(s) (EUC)	<i>The EUC(s) provide for MTF external connector for power MAIN power, 1x cable, and wireless LAN antenna for data communications and back-up signal path fire alarm warning between MTF and NM-III.</i>
<u>Neumayer Station III (NM-III)</u>	
NM-III	<i>Neumayer Station III - permanently manned German Antarctic research facility</i>
External Storage Container (ESC)	<i>Cold storage container(s) for spares, utilities etc. 7 - 8 km from NM-III. The ESC has no environmental control system and hence stored items need to be compliant with extreme Antarctic ambient climate parameters.</i>
NM-III EDEN ISS Control Console(s)	<i>EDEN ISS monitoring/commanding console(s) in the NM-III.</i>
Multipurpose Laboratory	<i>Facility in NM-III to perform food sample processing, plant sample drying and housing EDEN ISS freezer, analysis equipment, chemical reagents etc. The multipurpose laboratory provides a floor space of ca. 25 m² and the left side of the lab (upon entry) will be devoted to EDEN ISS activities. Space in the laboratory may be somewhat restrictive during summer field seasons but upon departure of the austral summer field team, a greater space within the laboratory will be available.</i>
Freezer Storage Facility	<i>Either EDEN ISS dedicated plant sample freezer or NM-III general freezer.</i>
Chemical Storage Facility	<i>NM-III facility for safe storage of EDEN ISS chemicals such as nutrient salts, acids, bases and disinfection chemicals.</i>
Skidoos	<i>Motorized manned sledge for access to external storage container up to 10 km from NM-III</i>
Transport Sledge	<i>EDEN ISS dedicated manual sledge for transporting supplies, waste, etc. between NM-III and MTF.</i>
Polarstern Crane	<i>Crane on the research vessel Polarstern for off-loading up to 25000 kg</i>

NM-III Crane	<i>Mobile crane at Neumayer Station III to be used for constructing Elevated Platform and MTF. Maximum load 10000 kg</i>
Elevated Platform (EP)	<i>The EP is a platform raised 2.5 m above ground level for mounting the MTF containers. The platform is reached from ground level by an inclined stairway. The platform is raised to reduce snow accumulation around the MTF.</i>
Other Terms	
DLR Control Center	<i>Main control center for EDEN ISS at the DLR, Bremen, Germany, for monitoring MTF science and house-keeping data and issuing commands.</i>
User Home Base	<i>Remote EDEN ISS user facility for monitoring science and house-keeping data and issuing commands.</i>
E-Nose	<i>An electronic sensor for detecting chemical off-gassing signature of pathogens such as E. coli and Salmonella Spp. Used in EDEN ISS project to monitor plant health status prior to human consumption.</i>
TransMADDS	<i>An aerosol based decontamination and disinfection system for sterilizing enclosed volumes of potential pathogens harmful to both plant and human health. Use in EDEN ISS dependent on concentration of pathogens detected by E-Nose and/or swabs/culture growths.</i>

2.2 Conventions

2.2.1 Units

The International System of Units (SI units) will be used throughout the EDEN ISS study.

For more information, refer to: <http://www.bipm.org/en/si/>.

Table 2-1: Common SI Units used in this document.

Quantity	Name	Symbol	Variations
Length	metre	m	km, mm, μm
Mass	kilogram	kg	g
Time	second	s	hr, min, sec, day, sol
Force	Newton	N	mN
Power	Watt	W	mW, kW
Temperature	Celsius	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	None
Pressure	Pascal	Pa	kPa
Illumination	lux	lx	None
Volume	litre	l or L	mL
Magnetic field	Gauss	Ga	100 MeV
Plant biologically active radiation	Total photon flux density	TPFD	$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{sec}^{-1}$ from 280 – 800 nm

3 Antarctic environment as analogue test site

3.1 Description of Antarctic environment

Typical weather conditions at Neumayer III are provided in Figure 3-1. The presented air temperature and wind speed data were collected using the Air Chemistry Observatory situated in proximity to Neumayer Station III and suggest the mobile test facility will experience minimum temperatures of approximately -50°C in the dark season, and summer temperatures reaching just over 0°C . Due to the approximate two months of darkness (and low sun angles) at Neumayer Station III (end of May to end of July), any plant production facility operating year round must incorporate electrical lighting. Snow accumulation and drifting is another factor that must be addressed by any external Antarctic plant production facility.

Figure 3-1: Neumayer III recorded air temperature and wind speed. Air temperature (A) is provided on an hourly average from Jan 1, 2010 to Dec 31, 2012, whereas wind speed (B) on a one minute logging rate is plotted from Jan 1, 2012 to Dec 31, 2012.

3.2 Neumayer Station III as a space analogue site for testing EDEN ISS mobile test facility

Justification for Antarctic in-situ plant production at stations operated year-round is anchored in the provision of improved crew nutrition and dietary variation. A compelling and tangible benefit beyond dietary considerations is the use of plant production units as horticultural therapy tools that can help alleviate some of the psychological stressors commonly experienced during isolation. The following outlines the advantages of the Neumayer Station III as a test site for the deployment of the EDEN ISS mobile test facility. Focus will be given to the maturation of the EDEN ISS technological and operational readiness for use on future space exploration missions.

Crew Size: The Neumayer Station III crew size varies with the season. During the summer season a team of approximately 40 to 50 people is maintained at the facility. During the Antarctic winter, a small team of normally nine crew members remains to maintain systems and continue annual science data collection. The size and duration of the overwintering team aligns well with current ISS crew sizes as well as those proposed in Moon/Mars design reference missions.

Crew Dynamics: Typical resupply schedules for an Antarctic station are very similar to current space station resupply schedules. There is a typical 9 month lag between resupply missions to Neumayer Station III, which exposes the crew to strong isolation pressure and the associated psychological responses. Unlike laboratory-based long-duration isolation studies, Antarctic crew members must count on technology to survive as there is no door that can be opened to 'end the simulation' in an emergency. Furthermore, although crew members are provided traditional recreational opportunities, growing plants is an activity where the output of a few interested crew members can be enjoyed by the entire crew. From this perspective, effects on the psychological well-being of the crew can be compared with real long-

duration space exploration scenarios, where some members of the crew can enjoy passive psychological benefits provided by the efforts of their crew mates.

Inhospitable Environment and Antarctic Treaty Requirements: The harsh environmental conditions typical of Antarctic research stations can only be found at a select few places on Earth. High winds, heavy snow fall (site dependent), low temperatures and seasonal dark periods lasting several months make this an environment where successful plant production requires advanced controlled environment technologies. The Antarctic continent is not only an extremely cold and arid desert, it is also one of the most protected, and biologically sparse environments on Earth. The Neumayer Station III greenhouse module is a high fidelity testing environment for microbiological experiments aimed at refining planetary protection protocols for long-duration human habitation of extra-terrestrial planetary bodies (e.g. Mars). The Antarctic Treaty and its associated Protocol on Environmental Protection place particular requirements on plant production facilities that provide noteworthy analogy to those required in future space-based systems.

Additionally, the initial deployment of the EDEN ISS mobile test facility at the Neumayer Station III serves as a first step towards greater and greater incorporation of bioregenerative life support systems into Antarctic stations. This provides an opportunity to validate complex integrated systems (e.g. air, water and food interfaces) under conditions relevant to the long-term goal of operating plant production facilities on the ISS and on the surface of the Moon and Mars.

3.3 Polarstern and Neumayer Station III Transport and Crane Limits

The maximum Polarstern crane, transport, Neumayer Station III crane(s) and the elevated platform mass limits are provided in Figure 3-2.

Figure 3-2: Polarstern crane, Neumayer Station III crane, transport and elevated platform mass limits.

4 EDEN ISS Software interface requirements

4.1 Software applications

4.1.1 EDEN ISS control software

4.1.1.1 *The EDEN ISS control computer shall use the Argus commercial application to develop EDEN ISS control applications as well as monitor and command the EDEN ISS Mobile Test Facility during operations.*

Note. The Argus system was developed by Argus Controls (Surrey, BC, Canada), a greenhouse control and environment management standard since 1984. The designed hardware is an essential component for handling the wide range of applications that the Argus system is capable of. It is exceptionally serviceable, scalable, and flexible. End of note.

4.1.1.2 *The Argus control system shall be hosted in a dedicated Argus server housed in the EDEN ISS Service Section.*

4.1.1.3 *User access to the Argus control system shall only be possible by authorized users using pre-assigned password.*

4.1.1.4 *Each user accessing the Argus system shall have a login profile that restricts access to only those functions required by the user.*

4.1.1.5 *The Argus system shall be capable of supporting several users simultaneously.*

4.1.2 ISPR control software

4.1.2.1 *The ISPR housed in the EDEN ISS Service Section shall be monitored and controlled via a dedicated laptop.*

4.1.2.2 *The ISPR laptop shall host the LabVIEW commercial application to develop ISPR control applications as well as monitor and command the ISPR during operations.*

Note. The LabVIEW (Laboratory Virtual Instrument Engineering Workbench) system, developed by National Instruments, USA, is a graphical programming language used for developing applications for data acquisition, signal processing and hardware control. End of note.

4.1.2.3 *The ISPR laptop shall be used to upload new programme code to the ISPR internal control board.*

4.1.2.4 *The ISPR laptop shall be used to acquire and store ISPR system data.*

4.1.3 EDEN ISS controlled sensors and actuators

4.1.3.1 *The sensors and actuators controlled by EDEN ISS via the Service Section main server hosting Argus are shown in Appendix A.*

4.1.3.2 *The sensors and actuators controlled by EDEN ISS via LabVIEW hosted on the ISPR laptop are shown in Appendix B.*

4.1.4 EDEN ISS Displays

4.1.4.1 *The Argus synoptic displays for monitoring and controlling the EDEN ISS sensors and actuators are shown in Appendix C.*

4.1.4.2 *The LabVIEW synoptic displays for monitoring and controlling the EDEN ISS ISPR sensors and actuators are shown in Appendix D.*

4.2 EDEN ISS external communications

4.2.1 EDEN ISS Control Network and Ground Systems

4.2.1.1 The EDEN ISS Mobile Test Facility shall be controlled either directly from the system server and ISPR laptop in the Service Section or remotely via the Mission Control or dedicated User Home Bases.

4.2.1.2 Data and commands shall be transmitted between the EDEN ISS MTF and the Mission Control/User Home Bases using the network setup shown in Figure 4-1.

Figure 4-1 EDEN ISS Control Network

4.2.1.3 The external communications from EDEN ISS shall be routed in either direction by wireless LAN to NM-III, and then via satellite to the Mission Control/User Home Bases.

4.2.1.4 The satellite data link shall have of a minimum bandwidth of 150 kbps.

4.2.1.5 A wireless LAN antenna shall be mounted on the EDEN ISS to transmit data and commands to NM-III over a distance of at least 400 m.

4.2.1.6 A dedicated PC shall be housed in the NM-III to monitor EDEN ISS status, store EDEN ISS data and to remotely control the EDEN ISS cameras.

Appendix A: Argus controlled sensors and actuators

Table 4-1 and Table 4-2 show respectively the location of the various sensors and actuators of the Argus system.

Table 4-1 lists all the sensor points controlled by the Argus system and provides information regarding subsystem location of each sensor, sensor ID, sensor type and whether Argus sensor type or user supplied type.

Table 4-2 lists all the Argus actuator controlled points and provides information regarding subsystem location of each actuator, actuator ID, function description and electrical characteristics.

Table 4-1: Argus controlled sensors

Sensor Detail				
Control Zone Prefix (3 Char)	Name or ID Per Sensor Point	Description or Type of Sensor	INPUT #	Argus Sensor Type OR Customer Supplied
TC1-IO [CP-A]				
NDS	FLOW METER TANK 1	FREQUENCY	CHA	CUSTOMER SUPPLIED
NDS	FLOW METER TANK 2	FREQUENCY	CHB	CUSTOMER SUPPLIED
NDS	LEVEL SWITCH SUMP 1 MAX		1	DRY CONTACT
NDS	LEVEL SWITCH SUMP 2 MAX		2	DRY CONTACT
NDS	LEAK SENSOR FEG		3	POT
NDS	LEAK SENSOR SES		4	POT
NDS	LEVEL SENSOR TANK 1		5	POT
NDS	LEVEL SENSOR TANK 2		6	POT
	SPARE		7	
TC1-IO [CP-B]				
	SPARE		CHA	
	SPARE		CHB	
NDS	TEMP 1 TANK 1	RESISTIVE	1	THERMISTOR
NDS	TEMP 2 TANK 1	RESISTIVE	2	THERMISTOR
NDS	TEMP 1 TANK 2	RESISTIVE	3	THERMISTOR
NDS	TEMP 2 TANK 2	RESISTIVE	4	THERMISTOR
NDS	LEVEL SWITCH FW MIN		5	DRY CONTACT
NDS	LEVEL SWITCH FW MAX		6	DRY CONTACT
NDS	LEVEL SWITCH WW MAX		7	DRY CONTACT
TC2-IO [CP-C]				
AMS-FEG	TEMP RH CO2 Light PHM 1	FREQUENCY	CHA	OMNI/CO2
AMS-FEG	TEMP RH CO2 Light PHM 2	FREQUENCY	CHB	OMNI/CO2
TCS	TEMP COOL 1: EXT HS IN	RESISTIVE	1	THERMISTOR
TCS	TEMP COOL 2: INT HS OUT	RESISTIVE	2	THERMISTOR
TCS	TEMP COOL 3: I&L HS IN	RESISTIVE	3	THERMISTOR
TCS	TEMP COOL 4: AMS HS IN	RESISTIVE	4	THERMISTOR
TCS	TEMP COOL 5: AMS OUT	RESISTIVE	5	THERMISTOR
TCS	TEMP COOL 6: AMS IN	RESISTIVE	6	THERMISTOR
TCS	TEMP COOL 7: ISPR OUT	RESISTIVE	7	THERMISTOR
TC2-IO [CP-D]				
	SPARE		CHA	
	SPARE		CHB	
TCS	TEMP COOL 8: ISPR IN	RESISTIVE	1	THERMISTOR
TCS	TEMP COOL 9: LED OUT	RESISTIVE	2	THERMISTOR
TCS	TEMP COOL 10: LED IN	RESISTIVE	3	THERMISTOR
TCS	TEMP COOL 11: FREE IN	RESISTIVE	4	THERMISTOR
TCS	TEMP COOL 12: FREE OUT	RESISTIVE	5	THERMISTOR
TCS	TEMP RADIATOR	RESISTIVE	6	THERMISTOR
TCS	TEMP OUTSIDE WINDOW	RESISTIVE	7	THERMISTOR
TC2-IO [CP-E]				
AMS-SES	TOTAL FLOW COUNT CO2	FREQUENCY	CHA	CUSTOMER SUPPLIED
	SPARE		CHB	
TCS	TEMP OUTSIDE EXIT	RESISTIVE	1	THERMISTOR
PDS	TEMP CONTROL BOX	RESISTIVE	2	THERMISTOR
SAF	SMOKE DETEC CPO		3	
SAF	SMOKE DETEC SES		4	
SAF	SMOKE DETEC FEG		5	
NDS	TEMP SUBFLOOR CPO 1	RESISTIVE	6	
NDS	TEMP SUBFLOOR CPO 2	RESISTIVE	7	
TC2-IO [CP-F]				
AMS-SES	TEMP RH CO2 Light	FREQUENCY	CHA	OMNI/CO2
AMS-SES	FLOW METER COND WATER	FREQUENCY	CHB	CUSTOMER SUPPLIED
AMS-SES	TEMP AIR IN 1	RESISTIVE	1	THERMISTOR
AMS-SES	TEMP AIR IN 2	RESISTIVE	2	THERMISTOR
AMS-SES	DOOR SENSOR		3	DRY CONTACT
AMS-SES	LEVEL SWITCH COND MAX		4	DRY CONTACT
	SPARE		5	
	SPARE		6	
	SPARE		7	
TC2-IO [CP-G]				
	SPARE		CHA	
	SPARE		CHB	
	SPARE		1	
	SPARE		2	
	SPARE		3	
	SPARE		4	
	SPARE		5	
	SPARE		6	
	SPARE		7	

Notes on this panel or zone :

LOAD TRANSFORMER PROVIDED BY THE CUSTOMER

NOTE THAT LED CONTROL IS THROUGH HELIOSPECTRA NETWORKING

MODBUS ANALOG INPUT DEVICE

TC-IO-MODBUS/BA0V (AI-MOD-01)		
1	NDS	L1 PUMP PRESSURE 4-20
2	NDS	L2 PUMP PRESSURE 4-20
3	NDS	L3 PUMP PRESSURE 4-20
4	NDS	L4 PUMP PRESSURE 4-20
5	NDS	R1 PUMP PRESSURE 4-20
6	NDS	R2 PUMP PRESSURE 4-20
7	NDS	R3 PUMP PRESSURE 4-20
8	NDS	R4 PUMP PRESSURE 4-20

CUSTOMER SUPPLIED
CUSTOMER SUPPLIED

TC-IO-MODBUS/BA0V (AI-MOD-02)		
1	NDS	PH1 TANK 1 4-20
2	NDS	PH2 TANK 1 4-20
3	NDS	PH1 TANK 2 4-20
4	NDS	PH2 TANK 2 4-20
5	NDS	EC1 TANK 1 4-20
6	NDS	EC2 TANK 1 4-20
7	NDS	EC1 TANK 2 4-20
8	NDS	EC2 TANK 2 4-20

CUSTOMER SUPPLIED
CUSTOMER SUPPLIED

TC-IO-MODBUS/BA0V (AI-MOD-03)		
1	AMS-FEG	AIR FLOW 4-20
2	AMS-FEG	OXYGEN 4-20
3		SPARE
4		SPARE
5	TCS	PRESSURE 1: FREE 4-20
6	TCS	PRESSURE 2: ISPR 4-20
7	TCS	PRESSURE 3: LED 4-20
8	TCS	PRESSURE 4: AMS 4-20

CUSTOMER SUPPLIED
CUSTOMER SUPPLIED

CUSTOMER SUPPLIED
CUSTOMER SUPPLIED
CUSTOMER SUPPLIED
CUSTOMER SUPPLIED

TC-IO-MODBUS/BA0V (AI-MOD-04)		
1		SPARE
2		SPARE
3		SPARE
4		SPARE
5		SPARE
6		SPARE
7		SPARE
8		SPARE

SPARE 4-20 interface unit

TC-IO-MODBUS/BA0V (AI-MOD-05)		
1		SPARE
2		SPARE
3		SPARE
4		SPARE
5		SPARE
6		SPARE
7		SPARE
8		SPARE

SPARE 4-20 interface unit

DIRECT TO ARGUS NETWORK

AMS-FEG	TRH PHM 1	modbus	EE071-HTPCA
AMS-FEG	TRH PHM 2	modbus	EE071-HTPCA
AMS-FEG	TRH PHM 3	modbus	EE071-HTPCA
AMS-FEG	TRH PHM 4	modbus	EE071-HTPCA
AMS-SES	TRH AMS 1	modbus	EE071-HTPCA
AMS-SES	TRH AMS 2	modbus	EE071-HTPCA
AMS-SES	TRH SES	modbus	EE071-HTPCA
AMS-CPO	TRH CPO	modbus	EE071-HTPCA

Table 4-2: Argus controlled actuators

Equipment Details							Electrical Details								
Control Zone Prefix	Name or ID Per Control Point	Description If Necessary	Quantity	OP#	Argus	Control Type	Power (HP or VA)	Voltage (V)	Phases	Max FLA Per Unit at 24V (Amps)	OL Req. From Argus	Ext. Limits Req.	Pilot Relays Req.	Total Current (Amps)	24V Loads
ELECTRICAL PANEL															
	RM-TX	POWER	1			RM-2TX75		120 VAC	1-PH	1.25	N	N	N		
	PS-GZ-01	POWER	1			SUB-PS24/SA-2		120 VAC	1-PH	1.4	N	N	N		
	PS-GZ-02	POWER	1			SUB-PS24/SA-2		120 VAC	1-PH	1.4	N	N	N		
TC1-IQ [CP-A]															
NDS-FEG	L1 HP PUMP	ON/OFF	1	1A		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-FEG	L2 HP PUMP	ON/OFF	1	1B		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-FEG	L3 HP PUMP	ON/OFF	1	1C		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-FEG	L4 HP PUMP	ON/OFF	1	1D		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-FEG	R1 HP PUMP	ON/OFF	1	2A		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-FEG	R2 HP PUMP	ON/OFF	1	2B		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-FEG	R3 HP PUMP	ON/OFF	1	2C		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-FEG	R4 HP PUMP	ON/OFF	1	2D		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-SES	SOLENOID FW TANK 1	ON/OFF	1	3A		D4		24 VAC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-SES	SOLENOID FW TANK 2	ON/OFF	1	3B		D4		24 VAC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
AMS-SES	CO2 INJECTION VALVE	ON/OFF	1	3C		D4		24 VAC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-SES	COOLER TANK 1/2 VALVE	ON/OFF	1	3D		D4		24 VAC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-SES	REC PUMP TANK 1	ON/OFF	1	4A		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-SES	REC PUMP TANK 2	ON/OFF	1	4B		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-SES	PUMP FW	ON/OFF	1	4C		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-SES	OZONE GENERATOR	ON/OFF	1	4D		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
TC1-IQ [CP-B]															
NDS-SES	ACID SOLENOID	ON/OFF	1	1A		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-SES	BASE SOLENOID	ON/OFF	1	1B		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-SES	ACID DOSING PUMP	ON/OFF	1	1C		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-SES	BASE DOSING PUMP	ON/OFF	1	1D		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-SES	A DOSING PUMP	ON/OFF	1	2A		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-SES	B DOSING PUMP	ON/OFF	1	2B		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-SES	C DOSING PUMP	ON/OFF	1	2C		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
NDS-SES	D DOSING PUMP	ON/OFF	1	2D		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
	Outputs available														
	Outputs available														
TC2-IQ [CP-C]															
TCS	COOL VALVE 1: FREE	4-20mA	1	1		P1A					N	N	N		
TCS	COOL VALVE 2: ISPR	4-20mA	1	2		P1A					N	N	N		
TCS	COOL VALVE 3: LED	4-20mA	1	3		P1A					N	N	N		
TCS	COOL VALVE 4: AMS	4-20mA	1	4		P1A					N	N	N		
TC2-IQ [CP-D]															
AMS-FEG	FANS CIRC L1/ L2	ON/OFF	1	1A		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
AMS-FEG	FANS CIRC L3/ L4	ON/OFF	1	1B		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
AMS-FEG	FANS CIRC R1/ R2	ON/OFF	1	1C		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
AMS-FEG	FANS CIRC R3/ R4	ON/OFF	1	1D		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
	Outputs available														
AMS-FEG	CO2 REGULATOR HEATER	ON/OFF	1	3A		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
AMS-SES	UV LAMP AIR	ON/OFF	1	3B		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
AMS-SES	UV LAMP COND WATER	ON/OFF	1	3C		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
AMS-CPO	HUMIDIFIER AIR IN	ON/OFF	1	3D		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
AMS-CPO	FAN AIR IN	ON/OFF	1	4A		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
AMS-CPO	VALVE AIR IN	ON/OFF	1	4B		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
TCS	COOLING PUMP RELAY	ON/OFF	1	4C		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
TCS	FREE COOLER	ON/OFF	1	4D		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
TC2-IQ [CP-E]															
AMS-SES	HEATER AIR LOOP	4-20mA	1	1		P1A					N	N	N		
AMS-CPO	HEATER AIR IN	4-20mA	1	2		P1A					N	N	N		
	Outputs available														
	Outputs available														
TC2-IQ [CP-F]															
AMS-SES	FAN AIR LOOP 1	4-20mA	1	1		P1A					N	N	N		
AMS-SES	FAN AIR LOOP 2	4-20mA	1	2		P1A					N	N	N		
	Outputs available														
	Outputs available														
TC2-IQ [CP-G]															
PDS	ILS LEFT SIDE	ON/OFF	1	1A		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
PDS	ISPR	ON/OFF	1	1B		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
PDS	ILS RIGHT SIDE	ON/OFF	1	1C		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
PDS	TCS	ON/OFF	1	1D		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
PDS	AMS	ON/OFF	1	2A		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
PDS	NDS SES	ON/OFF	1	2B		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
PDS	NDS FEG	ON/OFF	1	2C		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
	SPARE			2D		D4									
PDS	LAMP ENTRANCE	ON/OFF	1	3A		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
PDS	LAMP EXT	ON/OFF	1	3B		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
PDS	LAMP LOGO	ON/OFF	1	3C		D4		24VDC	1-PH	0.8	N	N	N		
	SPARE			3D		D4									
	Outputs available														

Appendix B: LabVIEW controlled sensors and actuators

The third column of Table 4-3 shows the location of the various sensors and actuators of the LabVIEW system. In order to facilitate integration, operations, assembly and maintenance of the EDEN ISS facility, all major parts are named and labelled according to a standard stated in the *Operations Nomenclature and Labelling* document. This document is relevant to all subsystems and personnel involved in EDEN ISS development. The leads on each subsystem have the main role in applying this document.

Major parts and spares connected to the Argus system will be labelled according to the following general labelling scheme:

zone.subsystem.position.part type.DAQ location.DAQ channel

For example, a controlled pump located in the NDS Drawer of the ISPR in the Service Section that is controlled by LabVIEW on digital output pin #4 would be given the designation:

SES.ISR.NDD.PMP.LDO.004

Major spares of the PCDU that are not connected to the LabVIEW system will be labelled according to the following general labeling scheme:

zone.subsystem.position.part type. serial number

For example, the spare of the same pump used in the previous example would be given the designation:

SES.ISR.NDD.PMP.002

Table 4-3: LabVIEW controlled sensors and actuators

Subsystem	Sensor/ Actuator	Location	No.	Sum	Controlled By	Control Type	LabVIEW Input	LabVIEW Output
Main Utilities Module	Thermocouple	SES.ISR.MUM.TPS.LTC.000/001	2	6	LABVIEW	Analog	2 wire TC	-
	Smoke sensor with potential free contacts	SES.ISR.MUM.FSW.LAI.210	1		LABVIEW	Analog	9-pin SUB-D	24 VDC
	CO2 line pressure sensor - gauge	SES.ISR.MUM.PSS.LAI.211	1		LABVIEW	Analog	0-10V 4-wire	7 - 32 VDC
	Cooling loop delta pressure sensor - differential	SES.ISR.MUM.PDS.LAI.212/213	2		LABVIEW	Analog	0-10V 4-wire	7 - 32 VDC
	CO2 1/8 inch electrovalve	SES.ISR.MUM.SOL.LDO.120	2	2	LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
Upper Utilities Module	LCD screen	SES.ISR.UUM.LCD.USB.001	1	1	LABVIEW	RS232	RS232	5 VDC
Power, CD&H Drawer	Thermocouple	SES.ISR.PCD.TPS.LTC.002	1	1	LABVIEW	Analog	2-wire TC	-
	TEC controller PR-59	SES.ISR.PCD.CTR.LDO.021	2	2	LABVIEW	TBD	TBD	24V
Nutrient Storage Drawer	pH sensor (in line)	SES.ISR.NDD.PHS.USB.003	1	5	LABVIEW	Analog	4 – 20 mA AI	14 – 30 VDC
	EC sensor (in line)	SES.ISR.NDD.ECS.LAI.3086	1		LABVIEW	Analog	4 – 20 mA AI	14 – 30 VDC
	Thermocouple (in line)	SES.ISR.NDD.TPS.LTC.003	1		LABVIEW	Analog	2-wire TC	-
	Pressure sensor (in line) - gauge	SES.ISR.NDD.PSS.LAI.111/112	2		LABVIEW	Analog	0 – 10 V 4-wire	7 – 32 VDC

Subsystem	Sensor/ Actuator	Location	No.	Sum	Controlled By	Control Type	LabVIEW Input	LabVIEW Output
	Conc. nutrient solution piston pump	SES.ISR.NDD.PMP.LDO.025/026	2	7	LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	Nutrient solution delivery piston pump	SES.ISR.NDD.PMP. LDO.027	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	Water to nutrient piston pump	SES.ISR.NDD.PMP. LDO.028	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	Water to delivery piston pump	SES.ISR.NDD.PMP. LDO.029	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	Condensate recovery piston pump	SES.ISR.NDD.PMP. LDO.030	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	UVC sterilizer	SES.ISR.NDD.UVL. LDO.127	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
Growth Chamber Drawer (Tall)	Substrate moisture sensor	SES.ISR.GCT.SMS. LAI.101/108	8	26	LABVIEW	Analog	3-wire AI	5 VDC
	EC sensor (in line)	SES.ISR.GCT.ECS. LAI.3087	1		LABVIEW	Analog	4 -20 mA AI	14 – 30 VDC
	pH sensor (in line)	SES.ISR.GCT.PHS.USB.004	1		LABVIEW	Analog	4 -20 mA AI	14 – 30 VDC
	T+RH air sensor	SES.ISR.GCT.THS.LAI.301/303	3		LABVIEW	Analog	4 -20 mA AI	5 VDC
	GC air pressure sensor – absolute/barometric	SES.ISR.GCT.PSS.LAI.109	1		LABVIEW	Analog	0 to 10 V 4-wire	7 – 32 VDC
	O2 air concentration sensor	SES.ISR.GCT.O2S. LAI.110	1		LABVIEW	Analog	0 to 10 V 4-wire	24 VDC
	CO2 air concentration sensor	SES.ISR.GCT.COS. LDI.402	1		LABVIEW	Digital	I2C digital 5 PIN	4.5 – 5.5 VDC
	Thermocouple	SES.ISR.GCT.TPS. LTC.004/009	6		LABVIEW	Analog	2-wire TC	-
	Electrovalve (for 4-electrovalve manifold inlet)	SES.ISR.GCT.SOL.LDO.001/004	4	17	LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	Piston pump	SES.ISR.GCT.PMP.LDO.005	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	Micronel D-series fan	SES.ISR.GCT.FAN.LDO.006	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	Direct liquid TEC (cooling/dehumidification)	SES.ISR.GCT.DHU.LDO.007	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	PTC heater	SES.ISR.GCT.HTR.LDO.008	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
Quadstepper motor (air exchange with cabin)	SES.ISR.PCD.QMD.LDO.010	2		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC	

Subsystem	Sensor/ Actuator	Location	No.	Sum	Controlled By	Control Type	LabVIEW Input	LabVIEW Output
	Micronel D-series fan	SES.ISR.GCT.FAN.LDO.011	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	Direct liquid TEC (cooling/dehumidification)	SES.ISR.GCT.DHU.LDO.012	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	PTC heater	SES.ISR.GCT.HTR.LDO.013	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	Electrovalve (for 4-electrovalve manifold outlet)	SES.ISR.GCT.SOL.LDO.014/017	4		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	Quadstepper motor (air exchange with cabin)	SES.ISR.GCT.SOL.LDO.018	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	Quadstepper motor (air exchange with cabin)	SES.ISR.GCT.SOL.LDO.019	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
Growth Chamber Drawer (Short)	Substrate moisture sensor	SES.ISR.GCS.SMS.LAI.201/208	8	26	LABVIEW	Analog	3-wire AI	5 VDC
	EC sensor (in line)	SES.ISR.GCS.ECS.LAI.308	1		LABVIEW	Analog	4 -20 mA AI	14 – 30 VDC
	pH sensor (in line)	SES.ISR.GCS.PHS.USB.005	1		LABVIEW	Analog	4 -20 mA AI	14 – 30 VDC
	T+RH air sensor	SES.ISR.GCS.THS.LAI.303/305	3		LABVIEW	Analog	4 -20 mA AI	5 VDC
	GC air pressure sensor – absolute/barometric	SES.ISR.GCS.PSS. LAI.209	1		LABVIEW	Analog	0 to 10 V 4-wire	7 – 32 VDC
	O2 air concentration sensor	SES.ISR.GCS.O2S. LAI.210	1		LABVIEW	Analog	0 to 10 V 4-wire	24 VDC
	CO2 air concentration sensor	SES.ISR.GCS.COS.LDI.403	1		LABVIEW	Digital	I2C digital 5 PIN	4.5 – 5.5 VDC
	Thermocouple	SES.ISR.GCS.TPS. LTC.010/015	6		LABVIEW	Analog	2-wire TC	-
	Electrovalve (for 4-electrovalve manifold inlet)	SES.ISR.GCS.SOL.LDO.101/104	4	17	LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	Piston pump	SES.ISR.GCS.PMP. LDO.105?	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	Micronel D-series fan	SES.ISR.GCS.FAN. LDO.106	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	Direct liquid TEC (cooling/dehumidification)	SES.ISR.GCS.DHU. LDO.107	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
PTC heater	SES.ISR.GCTSHTR. LDO.108	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC	
	Quadstepper motor (air exchange with cabin)	SES.ISR.GCS.SOL. LDO.110	2		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC

Subsystem	Sensor/ Actuator	Location	No.	Sum	Controlled By	Control Type	LabVIEW Input	LabVIEW Output
	Micronol D-series fan	SES.ISR.GCS.FAN. LDO.111	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	Direct liquid TEC (cooling/dehumidification)	SES.ISR.GCS.DHU. LDO.112	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	PTC heater	SES.ISR.GCS.HTR. LDO.113	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	Electrovalve (for 4-electrovalve manifold outlet)	SES.ISR.GCS.SOL. LDO.114/117	4		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	Quadstepper motor (air exchange with cabin)	SES.ISR.GCS.SOL. LDO.118	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
	Quadstepper motor (air exchange with cabin)	SES.ISR.GCS.SOL. LDO.119	1		LABVIEW	Relay	None	24 VDC
Illumination Drawer Left (Tall GC)	Visible spectrum camera	SES.ISR.ILL.VCS.LLA.002	1	1	LABVIEW	Ethernet	Ethernet	GigE 11 – 13 VDC
	LED lamp (incl. ballast)	SES.ISR.ILL.LED.LLA.001	1	1	LABVIEW	Ethernet	Ethernet	230 VAC
Illumination Drawer Right (Short GC)	Visible spectrum camera	SES.ISR.ILR.VCS. LLA.004	1	1	LABVIEW	Ethernet	Ethernet	GigE 11 – 13 VDC
	LED lamp (incl. ballast)	SES.ISR.ILR.LED.LLA.003	1	1	LABVIEW	Ethernet	Ethernet	230 VAC

Appendix C: Argus Synoptic Displays

This section shows all the operational synoptic displays that shall be generated by the Argus system for monitoring and controlling EDEN ISS.

The synoptic displays shall follow a hierarchical approach through the EDEN ISS system. The top-level display shall be the main EDEN ISS monitoring and control display Figure 4-2. From this main display sub-displays shall be initiated for the each of the subsystems as follows:

- ATMOSPHERE MANGAGEMENT SYSTEM:
 - SERVICE SECTION (Figure 4-3)
 - FUTURE EXPLORATION GREENHOUSE (Figure 4-4)
- THERMAL CONTROL SYSTEM (Figure 4-5)
- POWER DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM (Figure 4-6)
- LED LIGHTING SYSTEM:
 - LED Illumination main display (Figure 4-7)
 - LED Illumination single LED panel display (Figure 4-8)
- NUTRIENT DELIVERY SYSTEM (Figure 4-9)
- COMMUNICATIONS (Figure 4-10)
- ALARMS OVERVIEW (Figure 4-11)
- GRAPH REPORTS (Figure 4-12)

GRAPH REPORT EXAMPLES:

- TCS TEMPERATURES (Figure 4-13)
- TCS VALVE POSITIONS (Figure 4-14)

Figure 4-2: Main EDEN ISS Control Display

Figure 4-3: Atmosphere Management System (AMS) main display – Service Section (SS)

Figure 4-4: Atmosphere Management System (AMS) main display – Future Exploration Greenhouse (FEG)

Figure 4-5: Thermal Control System (TCS) main display

Figure 4-6: Power Distribution System (PDS) main display

Figure 4-7: LED Illumination main display

Figure 4-8: LED Illumination single LED panel display

Figure 4-9: Nutrient Delivery System (NDS) main display

Figure 4-10: Communications main display

Figure 4-11: Alarms overview display

Figure 4-12: Graph reports display

Figure 4-13: Graph report example: TCS temperatures

Figure 4-14: Graph report example: TCS valve positions

Appendix D: LabVIEW Synoptic Displays

This section shows all the operational synoptic displays generated by the LabVIEW system for monitoring and controlling EDEN ISS ISPR.

Figure 4-15: Main EDEN ISS ISPR (RUCOLA) Control Display

RUCOLA	ILL	ILR	GCS	GCT	NDS	PCDH	RELAYS	SET	LOG	STOP
Temp. Chamber (°C)			21.790						14/09/2017 15:14:49	REFRESH
Humidity Chamber (%RH)			60.000						14/09/2017 15:14:50	REFRESH
CO2 (ppm)			702.347						14/09/2017 15:14:51	REFRESH
O2 (%)			20.827						14/09/2017 15:14:52	REFRESH
Chamber Pressure (bar)			0.000						12/07/2017 00:00:00	REFRESH
Left Heater Temp. (°C)			40.184						14/09/2017 15:14:52	REFRESH
Left Cooler Temp. (°C)			17.375						14/09/2017 15:14:55	REFRESH
Left THC Temp. (°C)			23.238						14/09/2017 15:14:54	REFRESH
Left THC Humidity (°C)			60.000						14/09/2017 15:14:53	REFRESH
Right Heater Temp. (°C)			42.348						14/09/2017 15:14:56	REFRESH
Right Cooler Temp. (°C)			12.184						14/09/2017 15:14:57	REFRESH
Right THC Temp. (°C)			23.465						14/09/2017 15:14:59	REFRESH
Right THC Humidity (°C)			60.000						14/09/2017 15:14:58	REFRESH
Day(T)/Night(F)			0.000						12/07/2017 00:00:00	REFRESH
pH Solution			5.000						14/09/2017 15:15:01	REFRESH
EC Solution (mS/cm)			1.000						14/09/2017 15:15:04	REFRESH
Temp. Solution (°C)			23.607						14/09/2017 15:15:05	REFRESH
Left Air Flow (slm)			1000.000						14/09/2017 15:15:06	REFRESH
Right Air Flow (slm)			1000.000						14/09/2017 15:15:09	REFRESH
Substrate 1 GS2 Temp. (°C)			25.256						14/09/2017 15:15:07	REFRESH

Figure 4-16: ISPR (RUCOLA) Drawer Specific Control Display

Figure 4-17: ISPR (RUCOLA) Initialization Loading Display

Figure 4-18: ISPR (RUCOLA) Self Test Status Display

5 References

5.1 *Applicable Documents*

- [AD1] Antarctic Treaty. "The protocol on environmental protection of the Antarctic Treaty," Madrid, Spain, 1991.

5.2 *Reference Documents*

None.